

Studies on Infrared Spectra and Thermal Analysis of Rubidium Soaps

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The infrared absorption spectra of rubidium laurate and stearate were compared with that of corresponding fatty acid and sodium soap. The thermal transitions were studied by differential thermal analysis and thermogravimetry was used to study the kinetics of thermal decomposition of these soaps.

WHILE stupendous developments have taken place in the study of lithium, sodium and potassium soaps, the investigations on rubidium soaps have surprisingly lagged behind. Demarcq and Dervichian¹ studied the effects of dilutions and of hydrolysis on the transition temperature of alkali soap solutions and found that the transition temperature decreases from lithium to potassium but increases for rubidium soap. Laurent and Boyer² observed that the degree of hydrolysis of rubidium laurate is about hundred times than that of sodium and potassium soaps. Gallot and Skoulios³ identified three types of structural elements in the structure of rubidium soaps. Recently, there has been a renaissance of interest in the infrared⁴⁻⁸ and thermal decomposition⁹⁻²⁵ studies of metal soaps in order to obtain structural information in the crystalline state. Due to large applications of alkali metal soaps in industry, it was thought pertinent to study the physico-chemical nature and the impact of thermo-transitions on rubidium soaps. The present paper deals with the studies of infrared spectra, thermogravimetry and differential thermal analysis of rubidium laurate and stearate.

Experimental

Preparation of Soaps :

Rubidium Carbonate (A.R.) corresponding to 0.01M was weighed and dissolved in water and the solution was heated to 50-60°. Requisite amount of fatty acid necessary for complete conversion of rubidium carbonate to soaps (0.0 M), was melted and added to warm solution of rubidium carbonate with constant stirring. The soap thus obtained was digested on water bath for about 2 hours till evolution of carbon dioxide ceases. The excess of acid was removed by washing with benzene and the soap was purified by recrystallisation with methanol. After initial drying in an air oven at 100-105°, the final drying was carried out under reduced pressure. The soaps were analysed and the results of analysis

were found in agreement with the theoretically calculated values.

Measurements : The infrared absorption spectra were measured with a Perkin-Elmer Model 577 grating spectrophotometer using potassium bromide disc method. The differential thermal analysis was carried out on a Stanton thermobalance using alumina as a reference material and at the constant heating rate of 7.5°/min. The thermogravimetric analysis was carried out at a constant rate of heating of 10°/min on an automatic reading thermobalance.

Results and Discussion

Infrared Absorption Spectra : The wave numbers of the absorption maxima in the infrared spectra of rubidium soaps, sodium soaps and fatty acids are assigned and tabulated in Table 1.

The progression bands at 1200~1375 cm⁻¹, due to hydrocarbon chain, of rubidium and sodium soaps are weaker than that of the fatty acids. The absorption bands of C-H stretching vibration, the inphase vibration of CH₂, the asymmetrical vibration of CH₃ and the bands of symmetrical banding of CH₂ observed in the spectra of these soaps and fatty acids are given in Table 1.

The absorption band near 1700 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of fatty acids reveals the presence of C=O stretching vibration band of carboxyl group in dimeric state and confirms the presence of hydrogen bonds between two molecules of fatty acids. In rubidium and sodium soaps, two absorption bands of carboxyl group corresponding to the symmetric and antisymmetric vibrations of carboxylate ion are found at 1400~1450 cm⁻¹ and 1550~1600 cm⁻¹ instead of one band observed at 1700 cm⁻¹ in fatty acids. It is concluded that rubidium soaps are similar to sodium soaps and are essentially ionic in nature as absorption bands of carboxylate ion are observed in their spectra.

In the case of the thermal decomposition of rubidium soaps, where the soap disappears continuously with time and temperature and one product is gaseous, Freeman and Carroll's²⁶ rate expression can be written as :

$$\frac{\Delta \log \left(\frac{dw}{dt} \right)}{\Delta \log w_r} = - \frac{E}{2.303R} \frac{\Delta \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)}{\Delta \log w_r} + n$$

where E = energy of activation,
 n = order of reaction,
 w_r = total loss in weight-loss in weight at time, t.
 = w₀ - w,

and $\frac{dw}{dt}$ = values of rate of weight loss obtained from loss - time curves.

It is evident that the slope and intercept of the plot of

$$\frac{\Delta \log \left(\frac{dw}{dt} \right)}{\Delta \log w_r} \text{ against } \frac{\Delta \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)}{\Delta \log w_r} \text{ are equal to } - \frac{E}{2.303R} \text{ and } n, \text{ respectively.}$$

Fig. 2. Thermo Gravimetric Analysis
 —△— Rb Stearate
 —○— Rb Laurate

The plot of the weight loss of the sample, w, against time, t is shown in Fig. 2. The values of $\frac{dw}{dt}$ were obtained from this curve by drawing

tangents at appropriate times. The values of w_r were calculated from the total loss and the loss at predetermined time and then the plot of

$$\frac{\Delta \log \left(\frac{dw}{dt} \right)}{\Delta \log w_r} \text{ against } \frac{\Delta \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)}{\Delta \log w_r}$$

was obtained (Fig. 3). It is found that the order of reaction for decomposition of rubidium laurate and stearate is zero and the energies of activation are (+4.90) and (+5.5) K cal/mole, respectively.

Fig. 3. Thermo Gravimetric Analysis
 —○— Rb Stearate
 —△— Rb Laurate

It is suggested that the surface of the soap molecules remains completely covered all the time by the molecules of the gaseous product as the decomposition is fast. The rate of the reaction for such a system can be written as :

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{k_1 p}{k_2 p + 1}$$

where k_1 and k_2 are constants and p is the pressure of the gaseous product.

When the surface of the soap molecules is completely covered by the product, the rate of decomposition becomes constant and the process of decomposition is kinetically of zero order. Similar results for nickel—ammonia complex and zinc stearate were also obtained by Murgulescu and Segal²⁷ and by Rasheed and Bhohe¹¹, respectively.

The conclusion of the thermogravimetric analysis of rubidium soaps is that the decomposition reaction takes place in one single step and kinetically is of zero order, the activation energy for the decomposition of rubidium laurate and stearate are +4.9 and +5.5 K cal/mole, respectively.

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